

BASIC METHODS OF TEACHING LANGUAGE TO CHILDREN THROUGH VARIOUS GAMES

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ABSTRACT

This article provides information on the basic and useful methods used in teaching language to young children and provides important information on developing students' interest in language learning through the art of singing. The article focuses on easy and effective ways to teach preschoolers songs with a variety of fun games that interest the language. Many interactive games and fun activities based on language teaching are important in modern teaching methods. Today, children are interested in learning languages by using different techniques related to games and interactive activities.

There is a lot of work being done not only on teaching foreign languages, but also on finding and testing new methods of teaching all subjects. This is one of the most important issues facing education today. If in the past foreign language teaching was considered to be the study of this language system, in recent years the main focus of teaching has been to develop these students' foreign language skills. It should be noted that these goals in foreign language learning are not set by oneself or by others or individuals, but are closely related to changes in the sciences of linguistics and psychology and the social development of society. For example, consider the audiolingual method. The development of this method was

influenced by changes in linguistics, that is, the structural flow.

It includes the following factors:

- Teaching a foreign language should begin with teaching oral speech;
- Language learning is based on different structures, patterns of speech;
- Exercises should also be language-based exercises that require repeated repetition of language material;
- The choice of grammatical patterns and vocabulary should depend on the results of the comparison of the foreign language with the native language.
- Great attention to pronunciation is required.

A newborn baby's soul is like "pure cotton". As they said, what to write in the

spirit of the child in the style of "top-pure cotton" is absolutely at the discretion of adults. Therefore, what kind of person a child grows up, that is, what personal qualities are contained in him, depends on the experience that the child receives from life, the life concepts and ideas that he receives in the process of communicating with others, says John Locke to Angala. We need to carefully identify the tests that interest them, the picture tests with a variety of questions. Interest in talking to each child

Once they are identified, the appropriate songs, games, attention-grabbing and we begin the lesson with handouts of colorful, cartoon characters. First of all, we greet the children and discuss our topic. We will have small conversations with the children on our topic first, giving them their opinion and start with songs and games on our theme. Because it is easy and fun for children to develop an understanding of the topic and understand the lesson will be Slowly we distribute our interesting handouts and distribute them with games, for example: children's favorite color or favorite cartoon we can also ask for heroes.

After distributing handouts, we ask what they saw and imagined, then we explain the topic. Actually, young children may be distracted or bored quickly so that they don't get bored of being interested in different games, that is why teachers should conduct their classes with different games.

Types of games:

- Mirror play - the purpose of the selection is to observe the children's attention and development on the subjects of English.

- There is also a game called Find the Error. The purpose of this game is to teach children a lesson we can also understand why. For example, our topic today is numbers. We can teach children to tell numbers in English in this game. We place different numbers in the picture and show them to the children and we tell the kids to find the mistake. Children can learn a lot from the mistakes they make and can understand the subject.

- Our next fun game is if our subject is teaching numbers, we show the picture of the numbers and ask the children which number they did not know and children come out of the game and memorize a poem they have memorized.

- In the process of voice storytelling, children see pictures together with the teacher

they come out and at the same time pronounce the words.

- Cartoons in English - one of the best helpers in teaching English. Usually kids love cartoons and from watching them in a row enjoy. That's why English cartoons are for kids at the same time helps to solve many problems of foreign language teaching.

- Thematic environment; The teacher can create that environment depending on the topic children learn the language well. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen and others Traveling (travel) The teacher organizes a trip, to travel by what means (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane) where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA). This hoi students' vocabulary, language strengthens opportunities, grows outlook.

- Meaning that is difficult to explain or remember through songs and poems to

teach to tune letters or combinations that do not have.

- An example of this is when children learn the English alphabet by singing it can be shown to be more effective than simply memorizing.
- Games related to mental and physical activities.
- Cartoons; Although children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters

This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn a language.

- In the process of voice storytelling, children see pictures together with the teacher they come out and at the same time pronounce the words.
- You make fairy tales to make listening to English audio tales more fun one of the methods of therapy - you can use a fairy tale drawing.

But to draw a picture while listening, if the plot of the fairy tale is at least a little familiar to the child, works. So to the children when the tale is heard for the second or third time pen and paper are provided. The truth is, drawing while listening is what it is to deep skills of simultaneous perception and reproduction of information affecting process. Associative connections with what the child hears during the drawing process forms. Voluntary or involuntary, related to the plot depicted in the picture foreign words are remembered. Along the way, he listened and listened at the same time it should be noted that they have the ability to draw things. Four to five years old most of the babies under the age of heard the

information quickly do not have the ability to reproduce. But at the age of six, the information he heard listening regularly and in the form of repetition, drawing, application, etc. Children who reproduce listen, hear, understand and interpret at the same time develop their abilities on learning languages.

Teachers need to work with their students to maintain trust. Trusted relationships allow teachers to improve students and encourage them to higher levels of knowledge and help students take risks they do not accept (Jackson, 1994). Confidence between teacher and student is important as students develop their learning experiences. The key features and elements of a trusting relationship begin with knowing students 'names and pronouncing them correctly, exploring their family's heritage with students, and sharing the information learned with others (Jackson, 1994). Listening is the key to building trust with students (Brown & Skinner, 2007). Listening helps the teacher understand the student's words and adds value to the beginning of the relationship. Getting to know the culture and traditions of students and their families is very important in building trust with students.

Learning culture also contributes to and enhances the learning of the language and, therefore, there are many benefits of teaching culture in language classes. It gives students a reason to study the target language. It helps learners to relate the forms of languages to real people and places. These advantages, however, are not limited to learning the target language, but they are also related to understanding cultural diversity and peaceful coexistence of different people in the same world.

Some of such benefits of teaching culture were listed in Genç and Bada (2004) as:

1. Increasing learners' curiosity, interest, and motivation in target countries,
2. Nurturing tolerance towards different ideologies, religions, and cultures,
3. Giving learners a liking for the native speakers of the target language,
4. Playing a useful role in learning the geography, history, etc. and the target culture,
5. Helping learners to observe similarities and differences among various cultural groups.

In short teaching culture would lead the language learners to get a sense of the humanity of other people. Teaching culture in language classrooms seems to play a key role in forming the base for mutual understanding and collaboration in terms of cultural pluralism. Additionally, there is an indispensable link between understanding cultural diversity and peaceful coexistence of different people in the globalizing world, which seems closely related to getting over the problems of social stability, national security, the maintenance of human rights and humanistic values. This practice will also be in line with the tasks of the UNESCO regarding the world community, and its aim of elaboration of innovation strategies

of a modern cultural policy. For these reasons, intercultural understanding poses itself as an important issue in language learning and teaching. Incorporating the study of culture into the curriculum of foreign language teaching has been considered a matter of priority by language educators in the United States. Factually, it is believed that students cannot really master a language unless they have also mastered the cultural contexts in which the language occurs (Peterson and Coltrane, 2003).

In conclusion, teaching language to young children as an obligation not to be conducted in the form of a fun exercise, in several effective ways using the course as a basis for their future knowledge can serve. It is natural how important it is for children to learn foreign languages must be explained correctly by the circumstances. For example, the great thinker Abu Nasr Farobi was also fluent in many foreign languages, able to speak in these languages fluently, and created his creative work in foreign languages. Such an opportunity is the world of the scholar, he contributed to study, science and did great things. And one more great writer Alisher Navoi as our grandfather said, "He who knows the language, knows the world".

References:

1. Astafieva M.D. Holidays for kids learning English. – M.: Mosaic synthesis, 2009 y.
2. Galskova N.D. Nikitenko Z.N. Theory of foreign language teaching and practice. primary school: methodical manual. -M.: Airis-press, 2004.
3. Guseva L.P. We play, we teach, we learn - we know English we want - Rostov n / a: Phoenix, 2009 y.
4. Narimanova J.Y. ALICE WALKER'S BIOGRAPHY AND CREATIVE WORK IN AMERICAN LITERATURE.

European Scholar Journal (ESJ) Available Online at: <https://www.scholarzest.com> Vol. 2 No. 4, April 2021, ISSN: 2660-5562

5. Narimanova J.Y. The Role of Teachers' Cultural Awareness in Preparing to work with Multicultural Students. The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations (ISSN – 2689-100x) Published: September 18, 2020. P: 172-181.

6. Narimanova J.Y. The Significance of Comprehending Cultural Diversity Through Movies in English Lessons. International Journal of Engineering and Information Systems (IJEAIS) ISSN: 2643-640X Vol. 4, Issue 7, July – 2020, Pages: 53-58

7. Zemchenkova T.V. English for preschoolers. - M.: VAKO, 2008.

8. Ivanova M.V. English for children. - M.: AST: Astrel, 2009 y.

9. Trofimova G.S. Pedagogical bases of foreign language teaching (Subactics didactics). - Izhevsk: Udmurt University Publishing House, 1999.